

THE ISSUE OF FIGHTING DESTRUCTIVE FACTORS

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ABSTRACT.

This article talks about the issue and methods of combating destructive factors.

Of course, the public, the neighborhood, and the whole society should pay serious attention to the issue of fighting destructive forces and ideas with malicious intentions. Therefore, informational and analytical support for the fight against terrorism and extremism, that is, publishing manuals, brochures, books, posters, social advertising, publications on the experience and activities of law enforcement agencies, documentaries and videos, and creating websites, It is carried out through large-scale propaganda - propaganda.

In this article, the issue of combating destructive factors is analyzed and researched.

Keywords: *Globalization, human consciousness, spiritual threats, Internet, enlightened Islam.*

In the conditions of deepening processes of globalization, the political and ideological struggle between different forces and centers is intensifying, and various threats and dangers to the human mind, heart, and spirituality are increasing. For many followers of Islam, it is necessary to take into account that the way of life in Western civilization, the collapse of individuality, the institution of the family, the rise of social evils such as alcoholism, drug addiction, crime, prostitution, and suicide among minors are a destructive factor for human nature. Many religious fanatics and radicals see Islam as an acceptable alternative to the morally decaying Western world, and "Islamization" as a path to "neo-fundamentalism" that begins in Europe and leads to a "transnational Islamic community" via the Internet. In this case, it is natural that their plans and aspirations are primarily aimed at destroying the consciousness and mental and spiritual image of the youth layer of social existence. Consequently, cases of young people's indifference to national customs, values, and the laws of the true Islamic religion, knowingly entering the path of religious extremism and terrorism are still being encountered.

Article 5 of Law No. 167-II of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 15, 2000 "On Combating Terrorism" is devoted to the prevention of terrorist activities, which states that "the

prevention of terrorist activities is the responsibility of state bodies, self-government bodies of citizens and public associations, as well as enterprises, it is carried out by institutions, organizations by carrying out a set of political, socio-economic, legal and other preventive measures. In particular, the priority tasks of state administration bodies, local state authorities, citizens' self-government bodies, public associations, enterprises, institutions and organizations, officials, as well as citizens' support and providing necessary assistance to state bodies implementing the fight against terrorism have been determined. It should be noted that after the adoption of this legal-normative document, the level of quality of practical work and the fight against this social-destructive phenomenon in our country has improved, and the responsibility of state bodies and institutions of civil society, public organizations, and citizens has increased.

After some time, Uzbekistan's fruitful work experience in this field, and its contribution to the fight against terrorism was recognized by representatives of international organizations and international experts. On July 30, 2018, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Extremism" No. O'RQ-489 was adopted to regulate relations in the field of combating extremism in our republic. It contains legal documents, basic concepts, basic principles of combating extremism, main directions of state policy in the field of combating extremism, subjects of combating extremism, responsibility for carrying out extremist activities, and final provisions. Article 8 of the law is devoted to measures to raise the legal consciousness and legal culture of the population, to form an attitude of intolerance towards extremism in society, and the following is defined in it:

- conducting explanatory work;
- organization of legal training and education;
- development of educational-methodological and scientific literature on issues of combating extremism;
- strengthening cultural traditions, and spiritual, moral, and patriotic education;
- organizing and conducting scientific and practical events;
- improvement of educational programs taking into account the main directions of the state policy in the field of combating extremism.

Protection of public and private interests includes extensive social and legal preventive measures and organizational work. The issue of ensuring social order belongs to this complex of practical works. Reality shows that comprehensive preventive measures included in the social security system help to successfully implement personal protection. All of these processes are

closely related to each other and ensure public order, prevention of destructive actions, in particular crimes, and personal protection from various types of aggression.

The rule of law unites social (and legal) relations based on the simplest socio-moral rules in the sense of "behave as the law requires". These rules are based on social moral standards, which are of interest to the state, society, and citizens, without which social life cannot be imagined. These rules establish the normal conditions of human relations and thereby prevent crimes by protecting the individual, society, and the state from criminal offenses that are considered destructive activities.

Protection of a person from extremist and terrorist threats should be carried out based on these rules and by them. Such prevention is aimed at eliminating the risk of terrorist crimes, including other destructive behaviors in society, especially organized crime, and corruption. Social prevention, inextricably linked with the social and legal protection of citizens from religious extremism and terrorism, is of particular importance in this situation. Today, a lot of attention should be paid to the issues of socialization of young people, because in the social existence, the youth layer acquires skills and habits in a certain social environment, unites to specific interests, and is formed as an individual. Naturally, a person acquires the basic behavior, and external and internal cultural patterns typical for a particular social entity. To prevent destructive behavior from sprouting in the inner world (educational development) of the growing generation, it is necessary to take into account the factors that are distinguished by their values in each period of personal development. Socialization as a process of formation and development of a person continues throughout his life. This process is never complete and never complete. There are specific periods and stages of a person's socialization process, which should be taken into account and approached in a differentiated manner in collective prevention.

Social prevention should cover all activities of an organizational, social, and educational nature, to be inextricably linked with social, economic, and educational plans, and the strategy for developing the country's priorities. After all, social prevention comes from the social policy of the state. The legal nature of destructive activity, especially crime, is not opposed to its social nature, because law is always a social form. Based on the above, social prevention can be considered a specific type of practice in the fight against religious extremism and terrorism, and at the same time, it is a social activity. In social existence, social prevention as a unique positive factor ensures such a change in social relations, as a result of which conditions favorable for extremism and terrorism in society are neutralized or eliminated. At the same time, this type of prevention implements social control over the situation related to the formation and emergence

of extremism, and terrorism. The main task of prevention of religious extremism and terrorism is to control the manifestation of these socially destructive phenomena. In the system of prevention of extremism and terrorism, this is the control of society over their manifestation, and at the same time, it is public and popular control. It fully corresponds to the public's social opinion about religious extremism and terrorism and is firmly established in the public consciousness. The functions of public bodies and law enforcement bodies differ from each other, but their tasks and goals in the fight against extremism and terrorism are the same, which at the same time helps to develop active and productive cooperation. As a result, all the goals, tasks, and actions of these bodies are focused on one thing - to influence extremism and terrorism continuously, purposefully, and intensively. Achieving specific goals and solving relevant tasks is carried out by public organizations and law enforcement agencies using social tools and methods specific to each of them. This also determines their characteristics in the fight against various socially destructive phenomena in society, in particular, various forms of extremism and terrorism.

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